

***SESSION 8 -Isotopes in
Groundwater Hydrology
#327 BOL (F) TC:***

327_Flores Avilés_KEYNOTE

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ESTADO PLURINACIONAL DE
BOLIVIA

MINISTERIO DE
HIDROCARBUROS Y ENERGÍAS

Contribution of isotope hydrology to the knowledge of transboundary aquifer systems in the Plurinational State of Bolivia

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IAEA
International Atomic Energy Agency
Atoms for Peace

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International Symposium on Isotope Hydrology

Sustainable Water Resources in a Changing World

Introduction

- Problems
- Objective

- Quantity problems

- ✓ Population growth
- ✓ Climate variability
- ✓ Tourism

- Quality problems

- ✓ Mining areas

Transboundary groundwater is a key component of water security.

26000 km²

- **SDG 6.5** By 2030, implement integrated water resources management at all levels, including through transboundary cooperation as appropriate.

Bolivia (Plurinational State of)

Chile

Proportion of transboundary basin area with an operational arrangement for water cooperation (UNECE & UNESCO, 2022).

Objective

Understand the Tierra de los Lípez transboundary groundwater system and its functioning.

Develop a basin-scale
conceptual
groundwater flow
model

- Hydrogeologic domain/properties.
- Boundaries.
- Flow directions, sources and sinks.
- Groundwater budget components.

Study area

- High-altitude/arid basin
 - Geological framework
-

P = 222 mm/year ETr ~ 629 mm/year (Colcha K)

- Topography
- Climate

- Available information

- Tertiary and Paleozoic rock formations filled up with Pleistocene to recent sediments.

- Paleo-hydrology.

Methodology

- Investigation strategy
 - Mission field
-

- 90 measurements of stable isotopes of $\delta^{18}O$, δ^2H , $\delta^{13}C$

- 50 measurements of unstable isotopes of ^{222}Rn , 3H , ^{14}C

- Field measurements

In-situ measurements

Laguna Colorada pilot zone

Radon measurements

Results

- Mixing during recharge and groundwater flow
- Recharge altitude of groundwater
- Groundwater surface water interactions

- Glacial meltwater (f_{GR2})

- Recent meteoric water ($f_{EL TATIO}$)

- Geothermal fluids (f_{SM-1})

- Water from hydrothermal manifestations ($f_{M-118 A}$)

Spatial variations in stable isotope values

Legend

- Laguna Colora pilot zone
- Country boundaries
- Tierra de los Lipez Basin
- Lagoons
- Intermittent river
- Perennial Stream
- 5000 Topographic curves m a.s.l
- Faults
- Monitoring stations of isotopes in precipitation

Porous subdomain

- AcPor Porous aquifer media
- Porous subdomain boundary

Fractured subdomain

- AcPal Paleozoic aquifer
- Nag3-Nag14 Ignimbrite rock aquifer
- Nice-NPul Lavas aquifer
- RoPor Porous rock aquifer

Site investigation sources

- Groundwater wells
- Springs
- Rivers
- Lagoons
- Rock glaciers
- Other hydrothermal manifestations

■ ²²²Rn Mass balance model

$Q_{\text{effluent-LC}} = 165.950 - 921.945 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{year}^{-1}$

- Porous subdomain groundwater apparent ages 5.830 a 14.896 years.

- Fractured subdomain groundwater apparent ages 4.612 a 21.603 years.

- Last glacial-interglacial event of the Bolivian Altiplano characterized by the Tauca lacustrine phase.

Conclusions

- 2D schematic functioning of the basin-aquifer

Tierra de los Lípez transboundary groundwater system

Perspectives

- A guide to future data collection
-

To establish a monitoring network in the Tierra de los Lípez transboundary groundwater system to provide time series of groundwater levels and isotope data as a basis to forecast the effects of some future action or hydrologic conditions.

To investigate the boundary conditions of the Tierra de los Lípez transboundary groundwater system using isotope hydrology techniques, in particular, in the inferred western limit, where no-flow and groundwater discharge boundaries are hypothesized.

To generate science based information about the temporal and spatial variations of isotopes in precipitation to improve the understanding of the hydrogeological functioning of transboundary groundwater systems within the Plurinational state of Bolivia.

To improve transboundary groundwater security by improving scientific data and information exchange within the Plurinational State of Bolivia and Chile.

Thanks to the IAEA technical cooperation and within the framework of the RSA, the Plurinational State of Bolivia: i) improved the analytical capacity of its Isotope Hydrology Laboratory, ii) strengthened the capacity of human resources, and iii) assured development and continuity of scientific research.

'Assessing and mapping transboundary freshwater availability and sustainability using isotopes techniques within the Plurinational State of Bolivia, 2022-2025'.

- Collaborative science is required.
- Financial support for research is required.

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Collaborators

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Questions?
**Thanks for your
attention**

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